

Received: 17th January 2022Revised: 10th March 2022Accepted: 25th March 2022

Unveiling Academic Success: The Role of Study Habits in Secondary School Education

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Abstract

The study evaluated the study habits (SH) and academic achievement (AA) of secondary school students from government and private institutions in Kashmir. It aimed to explore the connection between SH and AA among students in Central, North, and South Kashmir. One district was randomly selected from each zone, and a total of 600 students (300 from government schools and 300 from private schools) were randomly chosen from 60 secondary schools. The Study Habits Scale (2019) by Sharma and Ansari was used to measure SH, while AA was assessed by reviewing students' academic records from the previous two years. The findings showed a significant positive relationship between study habits and academic achievement.

Keywords: Study Habits (SH), Academic Achievement (AA), Secondary Students, Academic record

Introduction

When we examine human history, we find that significant changes have occurred in every century. Consequently, educational processes have evolved and now place a new emphasis (Mangal, 2001). Education is an activity or procedure that transforms an individual's behaviour

from their innate state to their human behaviour (Taneja, 2003). This concept clarifies the fundamental reality that education aims to identify aptitudes and gradually prepare individuals for social interaction; thus, education that meets basic needs (clothing, food, and shelter) is vital for society's survival. Performance is simply the degree to which something is done correctly or incorrectly. Due to its importance to society, its relevance is particularly evident. Academic achievement, or performance in the educational context, is the outward expression of a student's study habits, which are shaped and reinforced by education. Establishing effective SH is equally relevant and beneficial for both academic and professional endeavours. Furthermore, this interdependence means that a student's academic performance and study habits play a crucial role in determining their own fate. Most people consider that students that possess strong SH would do better academically those who don't. AA, according to Sharma (2005), is a necessary evil because society and the economy place higher value on certain types of abilities over others. This creates a need to focus on factors frequently linked to academic success. Students are under tremendous pressure to earn good grades since academic success is thought to have predictive value and is used to open and close doors between elementary, secondary and university education as well as between higher education and particular social professions. (Sharma, 2005, p.69). Parents encourage their kids to aspire to the top of the academic ladder. This ambition places significant pressure on educators, learners, institutions, and the entire educational system, resulting in a focus on students' academic performance.

Study habits (SH) are typically defined as the regular activities that students engage in from the beginning to the end of all educational programs. These habits refer to the routines that students follow to complete their coursework, encompassing the entire educational experience. They generally indicate how consistently a student studies, which is shown through proper study habits like material reviews conducted in a supportive environment (Crede & Kuncel, 2008). Good (1998) states that study habits are the systematic, effective, or ineffective methods students choose for learning; these are the strategies they employ to ensure they comprehend the material (Azikiwe, 1998). To establish an organized approach to self-learning and perform effectively in their academic lives, students need to develop methods, create a study schedule, set aside specific study times and locations, and adopt certain behavioural patterns. These elements comprise the multifaceted concept of study habits, which impact students' transition academically, socially, and personally after school.

Academic achievement (AA) measures performance outcomes that indicate how well an individual has met specific objectives within educational environments such as schools, colleges, and universities (Steinmayr et al., 2014). It reflects the knowledge gained or skills developed in the classroom (Good, 1993). It represents the extent to which educators, students, or institutions have achieved their learning goals. The scope of academic achievement covers a variety of educational outcomes, depending on the metrics used for evaluation. Steinmayr et al. (2014) identify three types of indicators of academic achievement: curriculum-based criteria such as grades or test performance, cumulative indicators like degrees and certificates, and broad indicators like the declarative and procedural knowledge acquired through education.

Academic success is significant for individuals in nearly all cultures, whether developed or developing. A student's academic performance is essential and influenced by numerous factors including personality traits, school organizational culture, curriculum design, the teaching-learning environment, and home environment factors. These are all variables that can impact performance either independently or in combination. In summary, both nature and nurture contribute to creating successful individuals.

Review of literature

The concept of centres on an individual's academic AA. To enhance their academic performance, students must work diligently and exert effort. Developing SH is a key aspect of students' daily school lives. This significantly improves both their knowledge and perceptive abilities. By examining their SH, one can gain insights into their goals and aspirations. Raabia et al. (2017) suggest that lifelong SH can determine these outcomes. A chi-square test conducted on a student's from two colleges in Pakistan showed a significant correlation between SH and AA. Kaur and Pathania (2017) discovered that factors such as age, family income, and education significantly influence the SH of college students. Their research revealed a strong correlation between SH and academic success, suggesting that a student's age, family income, and educational background affect the development of their learning behaviours and are linked to their academic performance. Additionally, intellectual traits like cognitive ability are used to predict AA. Numerous studies have investigated the impact of non-cognitive factors, including study skills, motivation, SH, and attitudes toward academic success. Sikhwari (2016) concluded that positive research attitudes and good SH can significantly influence students' academic performance. To assess whether a significant relationship existed between the research variables, this study followed the methodology outlined in Lawrence's (2014) research, "Relationship between SH and AA of Higher Secondary School Students." The findings showed no significant association between AA and SH among higher secondary school students. Conversely, Mohammadi's (2018) study, titled "Relation study between SH and academic performance of nursing students in Hamadan," examined the connection between SH and academic performance among 220 nursing students at Hamadan University of Medical Sciences. This study found a positive correlation between students' SH and their AA. Additionally, Thiyagu's (2013) research, "The impact that SH can have on students' academic performance," evaluated how SH influence academic performance, considering variables such as gender, location, and residency. Data from this study, which utilized a standardized instrument to measure SH indicated no significant correlation between study habits and the students' academic characteristics related to gender, residence, and locality. Time management is essential across all aspects of our lives, including business, organizations, and education. In the realm of education, time is especially valuable for everyone on campus—students, instructors, administrators, and others (Sayari, et al., 2017). Research has investigated the significant correlation between students' AA and their time management skills. The study revealed a strong correlation between these two factors. Additionally, no significant relationship was found between procrastination, sociability, and students' academic performance. According

to Khanam's (2017) study, time management is one of the skills that influence students' academic success. A study focusing on Odisha medical students examined the relationship between their academic performance and time management. The study found that effective time management was crucial for improving academic success, as students who excelled in time management also achieved higher mean scores.

Priya and Dariti (2015) explored the extent of SH among students. Their study, which involved random sampling of 160 students aged 13 to 18, revealed that a greater number of boys exhibited poor study habits compared to girls. Their findings also indicated that students in private schools had better SH than those in public schools. Moreover, they found that the quality of education, along with students' SH and attitudes, significantly impacts overall educational quality. AA, reflecting students' SH's and attitudes, serves as a reliable measure of educational quality. Mendezabal's (2013) research, "SH's and Attitudes: The Road to Academic Success," supports the idea that students with effective SH's are more likely to achieve success. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that SH and attitudes are crucial to academic success, with the investigation showing a strong link between academic performance on licensing examinations and students' SH and attitudes. Furthermore, there was no correlation found between students' study attitudes and success-related SH's such as time management and work approaches. Akpan & Salome (2015) explored "The Impact of SH on Academic Performance." They selected a total of 100 students using the Random Sampling Technique. The findings revealed that although some students studied for up to six hours, most only studied for a brief period. Additionally, most students enjoyed independent study, while some preferred group study. In a 2017 study titled "SH as an Indicator of AA Among Senior Secondary School Students in Relation to School Type and Gender," Ali and Faaz aimed to examine the relationship between AA and SH among senior secondary students. Data was collected from 196 high school seniors from both public and private schools. The study assessed academic performance and SH's using the study habits inventory by B.V. Patel and the cumulative grade point average from their previous class. The analysis showed that students' AA was positively influenced by their SH, with female students demonstrating significantly better SH compared to male students. Additionally, the survey found that children enrolled in private schools exhibited better SH's than those in public schools. Singh and Mahipal (2015) explored "the relationship between study habits and AA in secondary school students." The research sample comprised 100 randomly selected high school students. The results indicated a positive and significant correlation between SH's and AA. Moreover, the survey revealed that secondary school students from government and private schools displayed similar study habits.

Need of the study

After reviewing the literature, the researcher found that there is a limited amount of research on secondary school students' SH's and academic performance. The way students approach their studies significantly impacts their academic success in secondary school. SH's are crucial for AA among secondary school students. This research will be valuable for school practitioners in designing interventions to enhance and improve the classroom learning environment. The

findings will aid teachers in developing student-centered strategies that encourage strong SH's in the classroom. Effective study techniques improve information retention and deepen understanding of the material. Additionally, the study will emphasize the importance of providing proper instruction and guidance to help students cultivate effective study habits and improve their academic performance. As a result, the investigator chose to conduct this study. The current research aims to evaluate the SH and AA of government and private secondary school students in Kashmir. Moreover, it includes a comparison between government and private secondary school students in Kashmir across various dimensions of SH. Furthermore, the study also explores the correlation between SH and AA among secondary school students in Kashmir

Hypothesis

H1: Govt. and Private secondary school students differ significantly on all levels of SH.

H2: Govt. and Private Secondary School students differ significantly on Scholastic Achievement.

H3: Govt. and Private Secondary School students differ significantly on various dimensions of SH.

H4: There is positive significant relationship between SH and Scholastic Achievement of secondary school students of Kashmir

Methodology

Descriptive research design was used. A comprehensive survey of the secondary schools of Kashmir division was carried out.

Population and Sample

The population includes all students studying at secondary schools in district Srinagar, Baramulla, and Shopian of Kashmir division. The sample comprised of 600 secondary school students (300 Govt. and 300 Private) was randomly selected from 60 secondary schools (30 Govt. and 30 Private), 20 schools were taken from each district through disproportionate random sampling technique.

Statistical Technique

1. Mean
2. Standard Deviation
3. t-test
4. Percentage statistics
5. Coefficient of correlation
6. Graphical Representation

Tools used

- SH inventory constructed by Deepti Sharma and M. Ansari (2019) was used to measure the SH of secondary students. The tool contains 48 items divided into 6 dimensions viz. Management of time table, taking notes, reading test book, Studying, Memorization & Preparing for test and exam.
- Scholastic achievement was assessed by consulting the previous two-year records of secondary students

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Levels of Study Habits of Secondary School Students with respect to Type of School

Levels of Study Habits	Type of School			
	Govt.		Private	
	N	Percent	N	Percent
<i>Extremely Good</i>	36	12.0	78	26.0
<i>Very Good</i>	60	20.0	71	23.7
<i>Above Good</i>	139	46.3	115	38.3
<i>Average</i>	61	20.3	34	11.3
<i>Below Average</i>	3	1.0	2	0.7
<i>Poor</i>	1	0.3	0	0.0
<i>Extremely Poor</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0

The table above illustrates the percentage distribution of sample subjects (students) across various levels of SH in relation to the type of school they attend. The findings indicate that 12% of government secondary school students and 26% of private secondary school students exhibit an extremely good level of SH, while 20% of government and 23.7% of private secondary school students show a very good level of study habits. Additionally, 46.3% of government and 38.3% of private secondary school students demonstrate an above good level of SH. Furthermore, 20.3% of government and 11.3% of private students possess an average level of study habits, 1% of government and 0.7% of private students have a below average level of study habits, and a very small percentage, specifically 0.3% of government students, exhibit a poor level of study habits.

Table2: Showing the percentage distribution of Scholastic Achievement (grades)among Government and Private Secondary School Students (N=300 each)

Grade	Percentage of Marks	Govt.		Private	
		N	Percent	N	Percent
A1	91-100	52	1	93	31.0
A2	81-90	73	24.3	106	35.3
B1	71-80	58	19.3	53	17.7
B2	61-70	47	15.7	30	10.0
C1	51-60	70	23.3	17	5.7
C2	41-50	0	0.0	1	0.3
D	33-40	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total		300	100.0	300	100.0

From the table, it can be observed that 17.3% of students in government secondary schools and 31% in private secondary schools have achieved an A1 grade. Additionally, 24.3% of private secondary school students and 35.3% of government secondary school students have earned an A2 grade. Furthermore, 19.3% of government secondary school students and 17.7% of private students have a B1 grade, while 15.7% of government and 10% of private secondary school students have a B2 grade. In terms of the C1 grade, 23.3% are from government secondary schools and 5.7% from private secondary schools. Only 0.3% of private secondary school students have received a C2 grade, and no secondary school students fall into the D grade category.

Table 3: Comparison between Government and Private Secondary School on various dimension of Study Habits.

Dimensions of study habits	Type of School	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Management of Time Table	Private	300	35.92	5.859	2.725	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	34.68	5.271		

Taking Notes	Private	300	28.32	3.942	2.872	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	27.40	3.933		
Reading Test Book	Private	300	31.04	4.577	3.164	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	29.86	4.507		
Studying	Private	300	59.60	7.845	5.656	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	55.97	7.845		
Memorization	Private	300	20.95	3.006	4.565	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	19.84	2.985		
Preparing for Test and Exam	Private	300	9.69	2.881	2.956	Sig.at0.01level
	Govt.	300	8.98	2.974		

The SH of the under-study population were assessed across various dimensions, including Management of Time Table, Taking Notes, Reading Textbooks, Studying, Memorization, and Preparing for Tests and Exams among secondary school students. Private secondary school students had higher mean scores on all dimensions of SH compared to their counterparts. The results indicate that private secondary school students exhibit better SH than government school students.

Table 4: Comparison between Government and Private Secondary School Students on Scholastic Achievement

Type of School	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Private	300	82.6820	12.25437	7.303	Sig. at 0.01 level
Govt.	300	74.8794	13.86735		

The examination of the table reveals a comparison of means between students from Government and private secondary schools regarding Scholastic Achievement. The table distinctly shows a notable difference between the two groups in terms of Scholastic Achievement. The mean score and standard deviation for students from private secondary schools (N=300) are 82.6820 and 12.25437, respectively, whereas for Government secondary school students (N=300), the mean score and standard deviation are 74.8794 and 13.86735. The calculated t-value is 7.303, which is significant at the 0.01 level. This

indicates that students in private secondary schools exhibit better Scholastic Achievement compared to those in Government secondary schools.

Table 5: Relationship between Study Habits and Scholastic Achievement among secondary school students (N=600)

Variables	Correlation	Level of significance
Study Habits Vs Scholastic Achievement	r =0.355	Significant at0.01 level

The table above presents the correlation coefficient results between SH and Scholastic Achievement among secondary school students. A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.355$) was found between study habits and scholastic achievement, with this correlation being significant at the 0.01 level. Thus, the hypothesis stating that "there is a significant positive relationship between SH and scholastic achievement of secondary students" is accepted. This indicates that improvements in SH lead to enhanced scholastic achievement, and vice versa. These findings are consistent with the study by Rabia, M. et al. (2017), which also demonstrated a significant relationship between SH and academic performance.

Result and Discussion

Based on the findings of the study conducted among secondary school students in Kashmir, it was determined that private school students exhibited significantly better study habits compared to their counterparts in government schools. This difference was evident across various dimensions such as time management, note-taking, and exam preparation. Moreover, private school students achieved higher grades on average, reflecting their superior scholastic achievement when compared to government school students. A notable outcome of the study was the positive and statistically significant correlation ($r = 0.355$, $p < 0.01$) observed between students' SH and their academic performance, underscoring the pivotal role of effective SH in enhancing educational outcomes. These findings emphasize the importance of cultivating and promoting robust study habits among secondary school students as a means to improve overall academic achievement, thereby informing educational policies and practices aimed at enhancing learning environments and student success.

Findings of the study

- There is a significant positive relationship between SH and scholastic achievement among secondary school students. Students with better study habits tend to have higher academic performance.
- Private school students demonstrated better SH and higher scholastic achievement compared to their government school counterparts.
- Private school students scored higher across various dimensions of SH, including time management, note-taking, reading textbooks, studying, memorization, and preparing for tests and exams.
- A higher percentage of private school students achieved top grades (A1 and A2), whereas government school students had a larger proportion of lower grades.
- The statistical analysis showed significant differences between private and government school students in both SH and scholastic achievement, indicating that private school students outperform government school students in these areas.

Conclusion

SH play a very important role in achieving the desired level of scholastic achievement. The aforementioned study indicates that there exists a significant positive relationship between the SH and scholastic achievement of secondary school students. It is also concluded that Private secondary students have better scholastic achievement than Govt. secondary students. This could be because private schools offer better resources and opportunities, like better infrastructure, libraries, labs, and smart classrooms with ICT use, lower class sizes, educational materials and so on. Some private schools may have stricter disciplinary policies, promoting a more focussed and orderly learning environment that can contribute to better study habits. Furthermore, private schools frequently have the flexibility to incorporate novel teaching methods and extracurricular programmes, which can favourably improve student academic performance. Consistent routines, time management, and active engagement in learning also contribute significantly to academic success. This implies that productive study habits play a pivotal role in the scholastic achievement of secondary school students of Kashmir.

Suggestion for further studies

Based on the findings of the study, SH and scholastic achievement among secondary school students in Kashmir, several suggestions for further research could be considered. Firstly, exploring the longitudinal effects of specific study habits over time could provide insights into how habits develop and influence academic outcomes across different stages of secondary education. Additionally, conducting comparative studies between different regions or socio-economic backgrounds within Kashmir could reveal nuanced differences in study habits and their impact on academic performance. Further research could also investigate interventions aimed at improving study habits through educational programs or policy changes, evaluating their effectiveness in enhancing scholastic achievement. Finally, exploring the role of digital

tools and technology in shaping SH and academic outcomes in the context of secondary education could be an area of significant interest and relevance in today's digital age. These avenues of research would contribute to a deeper understanding of how SH contribute to academic success and inform educational practices and policies accordingly.

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